

Table 1: Compilation of local observations and knowledge of reef passages around Ovalau, including their characteristics, fishing practices, marine species, seasonal patterns, and associated tabu or fishing restrictions

Name of reef passages mentioned by interviewee(s)	<i>Nailobaloba</i>	<i>Navusovuso</i>	<i>Nuku</i>	<i>Toki</i>	<i>Waitovu</i>	<i>Natubari (Levuka passage)</i>	<i>Nalulu</i>	<i>Gavo</i>	<i>Daveta tabu</i>	<i>Kalavo</i>	
Characteristics of this reef passage according to the interviewee(s)	Described as a very wide and one of the deepest passages in Ovalau with strong currents	A small and deep passage with stronger currents and waves than Toki passage	Fishermen had different perceptions about the depth of this passage	Described as “not as deep as Nailobaloba” at about 40-50m depth. Some areas of the passage are shallow.	The passage is wide but not that deep (~30m deep) compared to the other passages	Has the strongest currents compared to other passages in Ovalau and ~60m deep	Narrow and not that deep	Described as “similar to Nalulu”	No information	No information	
Fishing practices in this reef passage according to the interviewee(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Line fishing - Spear fishing (mostly at night) <p><i>Calling the Saqa:</i> First the fisher dives underwater and removes their mask and blows/forces bubbles from their mouths with the lips tight together. This attracts the Saqa closer.</p> <p><i>Calling the Mama:</i> The bait used here is the Kasikasi (hermit crab). The hermit crabs are crushed and thrown in the water; this attracts the Mama fish to the surface. Then the fishermen will knock on the boat floor / side with a rock, the knocking on the boat with the rock makes the Mama fish bite the bait.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - “Spearfishing sometimes, line fishing usually” - Siwa (line fishing) - Nunu (diving) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Line fishing - Spearfishing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Line fishing - Trolling - Spearfishing - Night diving 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Trolling - Line fishing - Spearfishing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Line fishing - Spearing fishing (night) <p>The fishermen travel further to other islands to fish due to less fishing pressure and bigger fish there.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Line fishing - Spearfishing <p>The fishermen use the new moon or when “the moon is getting small” to spear Kabatia [“Kabatia is coming out”] around Nalulu</p> <p>Dokoni is caught during new moon, when the “moon is starting to cut off”</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Line fishing - Trolling - Spearfishing at night <p>When the wind is coming from the south “cagi-ceva-ceva” it is a good time to fish here.</p> <p>“Especially good for catching Walu during strong currents.”</p> <p>“Same fish but it’s a different time when the fish is there.; if we go to Nalulu to get the Kabatia and we don’t catch any there, then it will be at Gavo. It’s the same for in town”</p>	Tabu area no fishing allowed.	- Line fishing	
Fish and other marine animals observed in this reef passage by the interviewee(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Babalao • Bati • Bu • Damu • Donu • Kabatia • Kawago • Maimai • Mama • Nuqa • Ogo • Sabutu • Saqalao • Saqaleka • Rosilao • Uluqa • Walu 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wahoo • Sharks (generally) • Hammerhead sharks • Bull sharks • Tiger sharks • White-tip reef sharks • Whale shark • Humpback whale • Sperm whale • Babale • Kawakawa • Sabutukula • Saqanivatu 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Damu • Kake • Kawakawa • Nuqa • Ogo • Sabutu • Saqa • Sharks (generally) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Babalao • Damu • Kabatia • Ulavi • Maimai • Nuqa • Ogo • Sabutu • Sabutukula • Saqadrau • Saqaleka • Saqanivatu • Ta-lele • Kawakawa • Vilu, Vilu-saqa • Walu • Wau 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Babalao • Kabatia • Kake • Kawakawa • Damu • Donu • Walu • Wau • Saqa • Nuqa • Maimai • Ogo • Rosinibogi • Sabutu • Sabutukula • Ta • Ulavi • Ta-lele • Ta-masimasi 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Babale • Babalao • Walu • Sharks (generally) • Wau • Ulavi • Ogo • Maimai • Sabutu • Sabutukula • Kawakawa • Kawago • Kabatia • Nuqa • Whales (generally) • Saqa 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Babale • Dokonivudi • Kabatia • Sabutu • Sabutu-damu • Sabutukula • Sabutuvula • Cucu • Walu • Dulutoga • Ulavi • Kawakawa • Donu • Saqa • Saqaleka • Saqalao 	No information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Donu • Dulutoga • Kawakawa • Sabutu • Sabutuvula • Saqaleka • Saqalao • Ulavi 		
Tabu and fishing restrictions	No tabu or fishing restrictions	No tabu or fishing restrictions	No tabu or fishing restrictions	Fishing tabu around the sandbank	No tabu or fishing restrictions	No tabu or fishing restrictions	Fishing tabu on the passage	Fishing tabu on the passage	Tabu area from Moturiki / sacred area	No tabu or fishing restrictions	
Other fishing areas mentioned by interviewee(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gau Island - Nairai Island - Naigani - Wakaya Island - Behind Wakaya Island - Cawaci - Makogai Island - Vatu-i-cake - Vatu-i-cake (only on the side) - Cule reef 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Loloi reef - Cakauseva - Balavu reef - Nukutabua (located south of Tokou) - Cakau-ni-yaga (bottom of Nalulu passage) [opening] - Tabutavasa (Further inside the Nalulu passage) - Nanuku (north of Tokou) - Cakaulekaleka – “town, other side of the reef, outside of the reef” - Reef flat a little south of Nalulu passage 									
Other Comments made by interviewee(s)	<p>Breeding ground for many fishes.</p> <p>Many different fish species can be found in Nailobaloba</p>	<p>Fishermen catch fish in Navusovuso when returning from Nailobaloba.</p> <p>Navusovuso is located north of Toki passage, before Nuku passage.</p> <p>Many different fish species can be found here</p>		<p>Strong winds and cyclones move the sand around and the sandbank (called “Cakaubulibuli”) was said to be formed after Cyclone Winston.</p> <p>There is no tabu on the passage itself.</p>	<p>Sabutu, Kawakawa, Kawago and Nuqa are caught in seasons, mostly during September-December.</p> <p>“Good passage for day diving”</p> <p>Whale season is August-September in Ovalau</p>	<p>“After Winston, the lighthouse at Natubari was lost and the shape of the reef changed.”</p> <p>In the colonial times, dynamite was used to widen Levuka passage.</p> <p>“Now people don’t really damage passages, no more poison fishing either.”</p>	<p>The tabu on the Nalulu passage was established during an agreement with an organization [Seacology] that built the Tokou community hall.</p> <p>The tabu is supposed to be in effect for 15 years, starting around the end of 2009.</p>		No spitting, no smoking, no wearing hats	Located going towards Gau by honeymoon island	

